

INNOVATIVE INVESTMENTS: APPROACHES TO RISK MANAGEMENT IN AN UNCERTAIN ENVIRONMENT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15340517>

Abstract. *With rapid technological progress and a dynamic market environment, innovative investments are becoming an important tool for sustainable development and competitiveness. However, the high degree of uncertainty inherent in such investments reinforces the need for effective risk management strategies. This article considers the key types of risks, characteristic for innovative projects, as well as modern approaches to their identification, assessment and minimization. Special attention is given to venture financing practices, stage investments, due diligence tools and diversification. Based on the analysis of domestic and foreign experiences, recommendations are formulated to improve the efficiency of innovative investments in conditions of uncertainty.*

Keywords: *innovation development, investment, risk management, uncertainty.*

Annotatsiya. *Jadal texnologik taraqqiyot va jadal o'zgaruvchan bozor muhiti sharoitida innovatsion investitsiyalar barqaror rivojlanish va raqobatbardoshlikni oshirishning muhim vositasiga aylanmoqda. Biroq, bunday investitsiyalarga xos bo'lgan noaniqlikning yuqori darajasi samarali risklarni boshqarish strategiyalariga bo'lgan ehtiyojni oshiradi. Ushbu maqolada innovatsion loyihalarga xos bo'lgan xavflarning asosiy turlari, shuningdek, ularni aniqlash, baholash va minimallashtirishga zamonaviy yondashuvlar ko'rib chiqiladi. Venchurni moliyalashtirish, bosqichma-bosqich investitsiyalash, tegishli tekshirish vositalari va diversifikatsiya qilish amaliyotiga alohida e'tibor qaratilmoqda. Mahalliy va xorijiy tajribani tahlil qilish asosida noaniqlik sharoitida innovatsion investitsiyalar samaradorligini oshirish bo'yicha tavsiyalar ishlab chiqilmoqda.*

Kalit so'zlar: *innovatsion rivojlanish, investitsiyalar, risklarni boshqarish, noaniqlik.*

Аннотация. *В условиях стремительного технологического прогресса и динамично меняющейся рыночной среды инновационные инвестиции становятся важным инструментом устойчивого развития и конкурентоспособности. Однако высокая степень неопределенности, присущая таким инвестициям, обостряет необходимость в эффективных стратегиях управления рисками. В данной статье рассматриваются ключевые виды рисков, характерные для инновационных проектов, а также современные подходы к их выявлению, оценке и минимизации. Особое внимание уделяется практике венчурного финансирования, этапному инвестированию, инструментам due diligence и диверсификации. На основе анализа отечественного и зарубежного опыта формулируются рекомендации по повышению эффективности инновационных инвестиций в условиях неопределенности.*

Ключевые слова: *инновационное развитие, инвестиции, управление рисками, неопределенность.*

The modern economy is increasingly oriented towards innovation, driven by rapid technological progress, globalization of markets and the need to increase competitiveness. In this context, innovative investments - investments in new technologies, products, business models

and scientific developments that can provide breakthroughs in various industries - are of particular importance. However, investment in innovation is highly risky and uncertain because innovative projects are often characterized by a lack of an established business model, unpredictable market reactions and an unstable regulatory environment.

One of the key tasks of the investor is to develop an effective risk management system that will not only minimize possible losses, but also create conditions for realizing the potential of high-yield innovation projects. This is particularly relevant in a turbulent external environment, where traditional methods of analysis and forecasting are losing their effectiveness.

Innovation investments are investments in technology start-ups, scientific development, non-standard business models and other projects with high growth potential. Unlike traditional forms of investment, they are characterized by a number of features[2]:

- High level of uncertainty - there is no historical data on the basis of which to make a forecast.
- Long investment horizon - return on investment may be only a few years away.
- Business model instability - the product may not meet market needs, and the company may change strategy during development.
- The key role of the team is that project success often depends on the competencies and flexibility of the management team.

These features make it particularly important to manage risks well at all stages of the investment cycle - from project appraisal to scaling.

In the process of investing in innovative projects, the following key types of risks can be identified:

- Technological risk -because the technology may be undeveloped or unusable.
- Market risk - the market may not accept a new product, especially if it is ahead of its time or does not solve the current problems of consumers.
- Financial risk - underfunding or inefficient use of resources can lead to the bankruptcy of even a promising project.
- Legal and regulatory risk - changes in legislation or the lack of a legal framework (often in the case of fintech, biotechnology, AI) can paralyze project development.
- Command risk - a weak or conflicted team, lack of leadership and entrepreneurial experience can lead to failure.

The following methods and strategies are used to effectively manage the above-mentioned risks[1]:

Portfolio diversification

One of the basic approaches is the allocation of funds between several projects, industries and start-up development stages. This reduces the chance of losing one bad investment.

Milestone funding

Financing the project in stages, when the goals are reached. It allows to limit losses in case of failure.

Due diligence

In-depth preliminary project review - analysis of technology, market, teams, financial model, legal risks. One of the most important tools of a venture capitalist.

Use of risk-based analysis models

The use of SWOT analysis, PESTEL, scenario modelling and stress tests helps to assess and model possible threats.

Partnership with accelerators and incubators

Investments in start-ups that have undergone acceleration programmes reduce technological and managerial risks, as such projects are already selected and prepared.

In developed countries, especially the US, Israel, Germany and South Korea, there is an established ecosystem of innovative investment. Venture funds, business angels, government support programs and university and corporate incubators play an important role[3].

The US is the world leader in terms of venture capital financing. Here we practice:

- Thorough due diligence prior to investment;
- Phased funding (with regular project reassessment);
- Active participation of the investor in the start-up management (i.e. smart money);
- Use of specialized legal structures such as SAFE and Convertible Notes to provide flexibility and protection for the investor.

Europe and Asia are also developing venture infrastructure, but with an emphasis on ESG innovation, sustainable development, energy efficiency and green technologies. Hybrid financial instruments and European guarantees for venture capital are used extensively in the EU[4].

Innovative investments play a key role in shaping the new economic reality, stimulating scientific and technological progress and providing the basis for sustainable development. However, the high degree of uncertainty inherent in innovative projects requires special attention to risk management issues.

The risks in this field have a multi-level nature - from technological and market to command and legal. Effective management of these risks is not possible without a systematic approach that includes in-depth project pre-appraisal (due diligence), portfolio diversification, phased investment and the use of specialized analytical tools [5].

Thus, the formation of a sound strategy for investing in innovation taking into account risks is one of the priority tasks for venture funds, private investors, corporations and development institutions. The development of digital risk assessment tools based on machine learning and big data algorithms could be a promising area for further research, opening up new opportunities to improve the effectiveness of innovative financing.

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